

Phase Equilibrium Studies on the Systems Cupric Chloride-Morpholine Hydrochloride-Water and Zinc Chloride-Morpholine Hydrochloride-Water

D. VENKAPPAYYA* and G. ARAVAMUDAN†

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Tiruchirappalli-620 015

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Isothermal phase equilibrium studies of the systems $\text{CuCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$ (MHCl = Morpholine hydrochloride) and $\text{ZnCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$ at 30° have revealed the existence of two double salts, $\text{CuCl}_2\text{.MHCl}$ and $\text{CuCl}_2\text{.2MHCl}$ in the former case and only one double salt, $\text{ZnCl}_2\text{.2MHCl}$ in the latter one. Some physical properties and the d-spacings for the above complexes have been recorded.

AS part of our study of the isolation of anionic chlorocomplexes of divalent metal ions featuring bulky and non-spherical cations such as morpholinium and ethylenedimorpholinium ions, isothermal phase equilibrium study of the ternary systems $\text{CuCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$ (MHCl = morpholine hydrochloride) and $\text{ZnCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$ at 30° was carried out. In addition to giving many useful details about the systems, the above study furnished the exact compositions of the starting materials for the preparation of pure chlorocomplexes. The chlorocomplexes isolated were also characterised by X-ray powder diffraction.

X-Ray Powder Diffraction :

X-Ray powder diffraction patterns were taken by using a Debye Sherrer Rigaku Denki 114.6 m.m. dia X-ray camera. CuK_α ($\lambda = 1.542\text{\AA}$) X-radiation was used by having a nickel filter. X-Radiation was done at a voltage of 35 K.V. and 15 amps. current for about 8-10 hours. The well powdered sample was rolled into a thin needle using quickfix. Where the complex was hygroscopic the sample was enclosed inside a Lindemann capillary tube.

Preparation and Treatment of Ternary Mixtures :

The phase systems were generally investigated as follows. About 30 gms of ternary mixtures containing the three components in varying compositions were taken in 30-35 ml capacity stoppered bottles. The compositions of the mixtures were generally so chosen as to yield ultimately 2-3 gms of equilibrium solid phase and 27-28 gms of liquid phase. The solids taken were well powdered to facilitate the rapid approach to equilibrium conditions. Care was taken to avoid meta stabilities in the system with the aid of nucleation using proper crystalline phase. Mixtures of three components

were prepared by several different methods so that the complete nature of the isotherm could be ascertained. In general, the mixtures were prepared as follows: (1) addition to powdered metal chloride to concentrated solutions of morpholine hydrochloride, (2) addition of solid morpholine hydrochloride to solutions of metal chloride, (3) mixing up of saturated solutions of metal chloride and morpholine hydrochloride and (4) controlled isothermal evaporation at 30° of initially unsaturated solutions containing suitable proportions of metal chloride and morpholine hydrochloride.

The stoppered bottles containing the ternary mixtures were attached to a horizontal rotating shaft in a specially constructed thermostat and agitated continuously at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ till the equilibrium was reached. The attainment of constancy in the composition of the solid and solution phases in the mixture, with progress of time, was the criterion for the equilibrium state. After the requisite period of equilibration (12-15 hours) in the thermostat the wet residue and the saturated solutions were separated and both the phases were analysed for metal and chloride. Zinc and copper were determined by the oxinate and iodometric methods respectively. Chloride was determined by Volhard's method. The amount of morpholine hydrochloride was computed by difference after estimating the metal and total chloride separately as follows. From the amount of total chloride, chloride due to the metal (calculated from metal analysis result) is subtracted to give the chloride due to morpholinium ion alone. From this the amount of morpholine hydrochloride is calculated. No hydrolysis occurred in these systems in any of the compositional ranges and no complication arose therefrom. Making use of the compositions of the saturated solution and wet residue the composition of the saturating phase in the wet residue was

† Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras.

determined by the Schreinemaker's method¹. Both algebraic and graphical extrapolation methods were used. As conventionally employed for aqueous salt systems the phase diagrams were constructed on a weight per cent basis.

The System $\text{CuCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$:

The presence of two new distinct solid phases in this system was indicated from visual observation itself. The two double salts are distinctly different in their colours. The crystals of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$, $(\text{MH}^+)_2[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$ are yellowish green in colour and needle like in shape. Crystals of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$, $(\text{MH}^+)[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$ are garnet red in colour and platy in shape. However, under the microscope the red crystals showed pleochroism.

Table 1 gives the analytical results of the saturated solution and corresponding wet residue phases. The phase diagram constructed on the basis of these results is shown in Fig. 1. In this system there are four solid phases represented by A, Y, D_1 and D_2 . The point A represents pure $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Y represents pure morpholine hydrochloride. The

FIG 1 THE SYSTEM $\text{CuCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$ AT 30°C

namely $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$ and $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$. The area of existence of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$ is very small when compared with that of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$. The line joining the water apex(W) and D_1 , the composition of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$, does not cut the saturation curve of this double salt. So $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$ is incongruently saturating and much care should be taken in the preparation of pure $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$. The saturation curve of the double salt, $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$ cuts the straight line joining the water apex(W) and D_2 , the composition of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$. This shows that the solid is congruently saturating and the preparation of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$ in the pure state affords little difficulty. The invariant point C represents the one particular composition of various components where $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ can coexist in equilibrium with $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$. Similarly, F represents the point where $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$ can coexist with $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$.

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the two complexes are given in Table 2. $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$ is a yellowish green crystalline solid which melts at $160\text{-}165^\circ$. The solid is highly soluble both in ethanol and water. The compound turns to a green liquid in less than 24 hours when exposed to atmosphere. The platy garnet red crystals of $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$ are much more hygroscopic than $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$. It is unstable in moist air and decomposes in less than half an hour to the hydrated salt, $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$. The garnet red colour of the compound is retained only for a short period even in anhydrous acetone solution.

The System $\text{ZnCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$:

The analytical values obtained for the compositions of the saturated solutions and the corresponding wet residues are given in Table 3. These

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY AND PHASE RELATIONSHIPS IN THE SYSTEM $\text{CuCl}_2\text{-MHCl-H}_2\text{O}$ AT 30°

Amount in gms contained in 100 gms of saturated solution		Amount in gms contained in 100 gms of wet residue		Composition of solid phase
CuCl_2	MHCl	CuCl_2	MHCl	
43.46	—	58.48	2.42	$\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
42.14	4.32	56.98	5.91	"
41.38	9.38	57.02	18.74	$\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$
40.78	15.26	44.46	29.09	$\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl}$
39.21	17.35	43.82	31.80	"
37.51	19.52	42.17	31.89	"
36.54	22.53	42.65	35.10	"
35.21	25.12	40.12	41.25	$\text{CuCl}_2\cdot \text{MHCl} + \text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$
34.51	28.02	30.70	40.31	$\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{MHCl}$
29.58	31.45	29.97	45.64	"
26.75	32.68	27.21	49.67	"
21.49	38.72	22.58	50.95	"
16.32	43.80	21.69	55.17	"
12.42	48.48	19.72	58.80	"
9.24	54.54	16.47	61.39	"
7.12	59.54	14.11	64.91	"
4.21	65.03	13.93	67.82	"
3.48	69.34	—	—	MHCl
—	74.23	—	—	

MHCl = Morpholine Hydrochloride.

solubility of cupric chloride increases in the region B to C on the addition of increasing amounts of morpholine hydrochloride. $\text{CuCl}_2\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has got an area of existence represented by ABC. The points D_1 (52.1 per cent by weight of cupric chloride and 47.9 per cent by weight of morpholine hydrochloride) and D_2 (35.2 per cent by weight of cupric chloride and 64.8 per cent by weight of morpholine hydrochloride) represent the two new solid phases

TABLE 2—d SPACINGS OF THE COMPLEXES

ZnCl ₂ .2MnCl		CuCl ₂ .2MnCl		CuCl ₂ .MnCl	
d(Å)	Intensity	d(Å)	Intensity	d(Å)	Intensity
6.96	m	5.75	w	6.19	s
5.00	m	5.15	s	4.18	m
4.70	s	4.52	s	3.45	s
4.04	s	3.95	m	3.07	w
3.70	w	3.76	m	2.78	w
3.53	w	3.54	w	2.41	w
3.35	s	2.91	s		
3.17	w	2.62	w		
2.96	w	2.40	m		
2.82	w	2.20	w		
2.71	s				
2.61	s				
2.49	w				
2.09	m				
1.99	m				

MnCl = Morpholine Hydrochloride, s=strong, m=medium and w=weak.

TABLE 3—SOLUBILITY AND PHASE RELATIONSHIPS IN THE SYSTEM ZnCl₂-MnCl-H₂O AT 30°

Amount in gms contained in 100 gms of saturated solution		Amount in gms contained in 100 gms of wet residue		Composition of the solid phase
ZnCl ₂	MnCl	ZnCl ₂	MnCl	
92.60	—			ZnCl ₂
69.56	9.90			
63.53	18.68			
58.45	17.76			
52.18	36.10			
44.26	31.87	39.81	47.47	ZnCl ₂ .2MnCl
38.11	36.23	37.06	47.70	
32.51	40.02	33.92	51.56	
27.96	44.11	30.87	51.07	
23.14	48.20	27.77	54.81	
19.24	52.52	26.01	37.45	
14.31	58.18	22.84	60.74	
10.85	66.25	20.07	63.03	
10.22	69.98	16.98	68.64	
9.82	74.26	16.96	71.55	
8.04	76.84	15.02	74.94	ZnCl ₂ .2MnCl + MnCl
7.54	77.02	7.52	81.84	ZnCl ₂ + MnCl
6.12	77.34	6.28	81.52	
4.25	76.28	3.48	79.72	
2.54	75.40	2.07	79.18	
—	74.23			MnCl

MnCl = Morpholine Hydrochloride.

FIG 2 THE SYSTEM ZnCl₂ - MnCl - H₂O AT 30°C

values have been plotted in Fig. 2 to get the equilibrium phase diagram. As can be seen from the figure there are only three solid phases in the ternary system at 30° represented by X, Y and D. X and Y represent zinc chloride and morpholine hydrochloride respectively. The point D is the intersection point for the several tie lines obtained by joining the points representing compositions of the solution phases and the corresponding wet residues and its position on the base line XY corresponds to a composition of 35.5 per cent by weight of zinc chloride and 64.5 per cent by weight of morpholine hydrochloride. By conversion to molar ratios the composition of this solid phase is shown to be ZnCl₂.2MnCl. The straight line joining the points of water apex(W) and the composition of the solid phase D, the loci of points which indicates various mixtures of water and ZnCl₂.2MnCl, cuts the saturation curve of the double salt. This

clearly indicates that the solid is congruently saturating in water at 30°

In the region J and K a limited solid solution of zinc chloride in morpholine hydrochloride is formed. This kind of limited solid solution was reported previously also in the system CdCl₂-NH₄Cl-H₂O.² As could be seen from Fig. 2 it was not possible to cover the equilibrium relationships in the entire range of compositions, particularly in the region rich in zinc chloride because in these regions very highly viscous solutions resulted which interfered in the attainment of equilibrium and the efficiency of separation of the solution phase from the wet residue. The points B, C, F and G represent typical solution phases which were very viscous and even on keeping these solution, over concentrated sulphuric acid for several days at 25-30° no crystals separated out. The water content in these solutions as could be inferred from the figure, was very low. For example, the solution represented by G, contains only 11.77 per cent by weight of water. Three conclusions can be drawn from the nature of the phase diagram. Firstly, the solubility of morpholine hydrochloride increases with small additions of zinc chloride. This is shown by the dip in the solubility curve in the portion K to J for morpholine hydrochloride. Secondly, beyond a certain limit, which was not precisely determined, there is a tendency of solid solution formation between morpholine hydrochloride and zinc chloride. This is evident from the observation that the tie lines do not converge at Y representing the pure morpholine hydrochloride phase but cut the base at different points.

Thirdly, there is a new solid phase appearing in the ternary system which is denoted by the point D in the figure.

Detailed phase studies thus showed that only one double salt namely, $ZnCl_2 \cdot 2MHCl$, $(MH^+)_2 \cdot [ZnCl_4]^{2-}$ is formed from the interaction of zinc chloride and morpholine hydrochloride. Employment of media such as ethanol or acetone instead of water also yielded only $ZnCl_2 \cdot 2MHCl$. The d-spacings for the new complexes are given in Table 2. Differences in the X-ray powder diffraction patterns of $CuCl_2 \cdot 2MHCl$ and $ZnCl_2 \cdot 2MHCl$ showed that the two complexes were not isostructural. In contrast to zinc chloride and morpholine

hydrochloride the new complex is very slightly hygroscopic. $ZnCl_2 \cdot 2MHCl$ is a white crystalline solid melting at 188° . It is highly soluble in water and to a limited extent in organic solvents like ethanol.

References

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